

Strategies for Sustaining Digital Libraries and Electronic Information Resources: A Survey of Nigerian Universities

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Abstract

This study investigated the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and electronic information resources (EIRs) in universities in Nigeria. A total of 15 universities took part in the study and the random sampling technique was used to select 90 respondents. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with a self-constructed online questionnaire was designed and distributed to collect data from the respondents. 75 online questionnaires were found valid and used for analysis. The data were analysed using frequency, percentages, and mean scores. The result established that there are functioning digital libraries/E-Resources Units in the universities. It identified the available EIRs to include free internet resources, electronic journals, and online databases, among others. The uses of these resources are mainly for finding relevant information, research activities, completing assignments, and accessing current and up-to-date information. The strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs use in the universities were: allocation of adequate funding, lecturers subjecting students to the use of e-resources for coursework, provision of adequate internet facilities, improving ICT skills of users, and marketing and promotion of digital libraries and EIRs. The study also revealed that the factors that pose as threats to the sustainability of these resources in universities are; epileptic power supply, frequent breakdown of digital facilities, lack of skills, inadequate number of computers to access digital information resources, and inadequate bandwidth for Internet access. It was, therefore, recommended among others that the management of universities in Nigeria should budget adequate funds for the library for the purpose of digital libraries and electronic information resources.

Keywords: Digital libraries, electronic information resources, library sustainability, university libraries, Nigeria

Introduction

Digital libraries have become integral parts of the library system as a result of the recent wind of change in information processing and handling processes resulting from the adoption of computing technologies in sourcing, organizing, accessing, circulating, preserving, and storing information. As such, libraries in order to remain relevant and satisfy the information needs of ICT-savvy patrons incorporated

the provision of digital resources as one of the major services of the library. Digital resources which are accessed using technological tools exist to complement the traditional library resources in print format in satisfying the information needs of today's users. A digital library is a library in which collections are stored in digital format (as opposed to print, microform, or other media) and accessible via computers, and the digital content may be stored locally or accessed remotely via computer networks (Candela et al, 2011). The evolution of digital libraries has revolutionized library services in many ways as users can now access library materials online regardless of their geographical location thereby making it more convenient, easier, and faster for library patrons. The emergence of electronic information resources is gradually sweeping away the print forms of information resources (Igwela & Opara, 2020).

Electronic information resources (EIRs) are information provided in electronic form and these include databases, CD-ROM, electronic books, electronic journals, and other computer-based electronic networks (Uwandu, 2022). EIRs are provided and made accessible in digital libraries, and access to them is not limited by time, location, or space constraints. In other words, the value of digital libraries and electronic information resources can never be over-emphasized in libraries, particularly university libraries. University libraries are libraries situated in universities. They are primarily established to support teaching, learning, and research activities in the university. The library users include students (undergraduates and postgraduates), lecturers, and academic and non-academic staff of the university. University libraries also document and preserve research publications from the university such as dissertations, theses, research projects, conference proceedings, journals, and textbooks. The ability of the universities to excel and succeed in their goals related to teaching, learning, research, and communication of knowledge depends to a great extent on the library's capability in providing the needed information for the university community. Libraries universally are taken as the bedrock of academic activities; thus, they had continued to make efforts targeted at ensuring that information resources are not only made available but are also made accessible in a format and platform that are most desirable and convenient for the user community.

The availability of these resources is globally acknowledged to have received general acceptance by today's library users who most often prefer to access information from the comfort of their homes without physical visits to the library. Nigerian university libraries are not left out in this trend as many of them have expanded their collection formats to include EIRs which in the context of this work are also taken as digital resources. Eneh & Opara (2022) confirmed this by stating that university libraries in Nigeria now subscribe to EIRs to complement their print collections for easy access and optimum use. Regrettably, it has been observed that digital libraries and EIRs in universities are grossly underutilized. A similar view was shared by Ojukwu (2017) who stated that electronic information resources are facing some challenges affecting their use, and that such include poor research skills and lack of technological skills. Obviously, this situation is a threat to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in university

libraries. It is on this background that this research has been orchestrated to find out the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

- To investigate the availability of functioning digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.
- To find out the uses of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.
- To determine the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.
- To identify the factors that pose as threat to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.

Research questions

- 1 Are there functioning digital libraries and EIRs available in universities in Nigeria?
- 2 What are the uses of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria?
- 3 What are the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria?
- 4 What are the factors that pose as threat to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria?

Theoretical framework

This study is hinged on DELOS Digital Library Reference Model which was a product of brainstorming workshops of stakeholders in the digital library field in 2007. The model was aimed at addressing major entities and their relationships in the digital library universe. The model is built on six main domains: content, user, functionality, policy, quality, and architecture (Casarova, 2007). The first is Content which represents the information managed in the digital library. The second, user refers to the actors interacting with the system. The digital library connects users with information content that supports them in meeting their information needs. The third, functionality refers to the ability of the system or facilities (digital library) to support and aid the achievement of a set goal which in this study is to ensure that users have unhindered access to their needed information. The fourth, policy represents the rules and conditions, including digital rights governing the operation of the elements of the digital library such as privacy and digital rights management. The fifth, quality stands for the aspects of digital library systems to be considered from a quality point of view and the general functionality of the systems. The sixth, architecture refers to the software and hardware constituents needed for optimal functionality of the system. Moreover, this model is relevant to the current study as it can be applied in this research based on the fact that it can help librarians and library users to understand the relationship between the major entities of a digital library thereby contributing to the usage and sustenance of digital libraries and other electronic information resources.

Literature review

Digital libraries and electronic information resources form a major part of the library's collection and have become very essential for learning, teaching, and research activities that take place in institutions of higher learning. According to Mukhtar and Maidabino (2021), the advent of information technology

has led to the growth of digital resources, or EIRs, and has made them significant parts of the library collection. Iroaganachi and Izuagbe (2018) affirmed that university libraries in Nigeria subscribe to, and manage electronic resources so as to enhance the quality of the academic and research output of their institutions. However, contrary to expectations, the availability of electronic information resources has not brought the needed satisfaction, as evidenced in Anyim (2018) who reported in his research on “university e-libraries use in Kogi State, Nigeria” that respondents are dissatisfied with the prevailing state of these e-libraries in the area of information resources and services delivery 118 (49%).

There are several electronic information resources made available in university libraries today as a result of the adoption of the new normal information technologies. Mukhtar and Maidabino (2021) in their study on the management of EIRs in Nigerian university libraries noted that the available ones in the university libraries are electronic journals, electronic books, online databases, and CD-ROM databases. This is in line with Ikoja-Odongo and Okello-Obura (2013) who listed EIRs in university libraries to include: The Internet, electronic journals, online databases, and CD-ROM databases.

In relation to the use of digital libraries and EIRs, Priyadharshini, Janakiraman & Subramanian (2015) cited by Abbas and Song (2020) conducted a study on “Awareness in the usage of e-Resources among users at Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai: A case study”. The outcome of the study revealed that the most frequently used EIRs are E-journals (70%); followed by e-books (65%) and online databases (50%), while the least used of them are e-archives and CD ROM databases (5%). Abbas and Song (2020) documented from their own findings that the students utilize E-dissertations, E-books, and E-Journals (mean=4.00), Online databases, and Scholarly Websites (mean=3.63) and CD-ROM/DVD Searching Services (mean=3.54) for research.

Digital libraries and EIRs are used in universities for varying purposes which include writing term papers, doing class assignments, research works, and updating one’s knowledge on trends in his/her profession. Osinulu (2020) in his research on “Awareness and use of EIRs” in which the descriptive research design was adopted, established that the major purposes for which students use these resources are for research activities and completion of assignments. Daramola’s (2016) research outcome on the “Perception and Utilization of Electronic Resources by Undergraduate Students: The Case of the Federal University of Technology Library, Akure also shows that the majority of the respondents (83.33%) visited the e-resources section in order to access their e-mails and 82.22% to do assignments. The findings here corroborate Nwalo and Babarinde (2022) results which revealed that 812 (69.2%) of the respondents used the Internet for classwork/assignments and 624(53.2%) for research projects.

Another study carried out by Owolabi et.al (2016) on “Utilization of electronic information resources by undergraduate students of University of Ibadan: a case study of Social Sciences and Education” showed that the benefits derived by undergraduate students from the use of these resources are; access to current and up-to-date information, access to a wider range of information, easier access to information, faster access to information, and improved academic performance.

Strategies for sustaining digital libraries and electronic information resources have become needful, especially at a time when the relevance of digital libraries and electronic information resources use is fraught with challenges. The strategies found out by Isaac's (2017) study on "Awareness and usage of electronic information resources among Postgraduate students of library and information science in southern Nigeria" are adequate allocation of resources, subscription of needed resources, developed digital repository, information literacy skills and marketing, and promotion of digital information services and resources.

In the area of factors that pose a threat to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs' use in university libraries, Urhiewhu (2015) identified epileptic power supply, non-availability of online databases, inadequate number of computers to access digital information resources, inadequate bandwidth, network problems, lack of skill to access digital information resources in local and foreign databases, lack of formal training on internet resources' use, and server slowness. Ankrah & Atuase (2018) research outcome on the use of electronic resources by postgraduate students of the University of Cape Coast corroborated this submission. The respondents in their study identified poor internet connection 183(72.6%) as the most significant constraint for ineffective access to e-resources. Other challenges established in their study include power outages in the library 173(68.7%), insufficient skills 165(65.5%), limited subscribed titles 157(62.3%), and inadequate computers 143(56.7%). Edem & Egbe (2016) and Ternenge and Kashimana (2019) also have the same findings in their studies. Ojukwu (2017) disclosed from his study on "Sustainability strategies for EIRs services in university libraries" that the challenges include licensing costs, inadequate Internet, and funding.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was librarians in universities in Nigeria. However, a total of 15 universities took part in the study and a random sampling technique was used to select 90 respondents. A self-constructed online questionnaire was designed and distributed to collect the data from the respondents. The online questionnaire was divided into five (5) sections which included the demographic information of the respondents, the available digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria, the uses of digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria, strategies for sustaining digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria and factors militating against digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria.

A total of 90 respondents filled out the online questionnaire but 75 were found to be valid and used for analysis as the other 15 were not properly filled. The data were analyzed using percentages and mean scores. Using the four-point Likert scale, the mean was calculated as $4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 10 \div 4 = 2.50$

Decision rule: Based on the mean of 2.50, the decision was that a mean of 2.50 and above is accepted while any item with a mean below 2.50 is rejected.

Analysis and Discussion of Results

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Fig. 1. Sex

The respondents consisted of 75 librarians from 15 universities in Nigeria. The result on the sex of the respondents indicated that 57% were females while the remaining 43% were males.

Fig. 2. Educational Qualification

The outcome on educational qualification of the respondents indicated that there were 17 (23%) PhD holders, 23 (31%) had MLIS and 35 (46%) had BLIS.

Research question one: What are the digital libraries and electronic information resources available in universities in Nigeria?

Table 1: Availability of functioning digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria

S/N	ITEM	MEAN	DECISION
1.	There is presence of a functioning digital library/E-Resources Unit in the library	3.8	Accepted
2	The library has digital institutional repositories	3.8	Accepted

3.	The library provides access to free internet resources	3.8	Accepted
5.	The library has an online public access catalogue (OPAC)	2.7	Accepted
6.	The library has online databases	2.6	Accepted
7.	The library has electronic journals	2.5	Accepted
8.	The library has CD-ROM databases	2.3	Rejected

Table 1 shows the available digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria. The responses from the respondents indicated the acceptance rate for the availability of a functioning digital library/E-Resources Unit in the library as well as the presence of digital institutional repositories as 3.8, respectively, access to free Internet resources (3.8), electronic journals (2.5), online databases (2.6), and online public access catalogue (2.7). On the other hand, respondents rejected the availability of the CD-ROM database (2.3) in universities in Nigeria.

Research question two: what are the uses of digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria?

Table 2.: Uses of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria

S/N	ITEM	MEAN	DECISION
1.	They are used in finding relevant needed information	3.7	Accepted
2.	They are used for research activities	3.6	Accepted
3.	They are used for easier access to information	3.5	Accepted
4.	They are used for completing assignments	3.0	Accepted
5.	They are used to access current and up-to-date information	2.8	Accepted
6.	They are used to access a wide range of information	2.7	Accepted

Table 2 above shows the uses of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria. The result indicated that the digital libraries and the EIRs are used in finding relevant needed information (3.7), research activities (3.6), completing assignments (3.0), accessing current and up-to-date information (2.8), accessing a wide range of information (2.7) and easier access to information (3.5).

Research question three: What are the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and electronic information resources in universities in Nigeria?

Table 3: Strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in Universities in Nigeria

S/N	ITEM	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Adequate funding allocation	3.7	Accepted
2.	Development of digital repositories	3.6	Accepted
3.	Lecturers subjecting students to the use of e-resources for coursework	3.6	Accepted
4.	Adequate subscription to needed online resources	3.5	Accepted
5.	Provision of adequate internet facilities	3.4	Accepted
6.	More networked computers should be purchased by the universities	3.2	Accepted

7.	ICT skills of users should be improved	3.1	Accepted
8.	Conducting information literacy skills training	3.0	Accepted
9.	Marketing and promotion of digital libraries and EIRs	2.7	Accepted

Table 3 shows respondents' opinions on the strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria. These include adequate funding allocation (3.7), development of digital repositories (3.6), lecturers subjecting students to the use of e-resources for coursework (3.6), Adequate subscription to needed online resources (3.5), provision of adequate internet facilities (3.4), improving ICT skills of users (3.1), conducting information literacy skills training (3.0), and marketing and promotion of digital libraries and electronic information resources (2.7).

Research question four: What are the factors that pose as threats to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria?

Table 4: Factors that pose as threats to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria.

S/N	ITEM	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Epileptic power supply	3.7	Accepted
2.	Frequent breakdown of digital facilities	3.5	Accepted
3.	Lack of skills to access digital information resources and databases	3.4	Accepted
5.	Inadequate number of computers to access digital information resources and databases	3.0	Accepted
6.	Inadequate bandwidth	2.7	Accepted

Concerning the factors that pose as threat to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria, the majority of the respondents indicated epileptic power supply (3.7) as the most severe factor. Other factors indicated include; frequent breakdown of digital facilities (3.5), lack of skills to access digital information resources and databases (3.4), the inadequate number of computers to access digital information resources (3.0), and inadequate bandwidth for Internet access (2.7).

Discussion of findings

For clarity purposes, the discussion of findings for this study is subdivided into four (4) following the research objectives.

Availability of functioning digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria

The study revealed that the universities have functioning digital library/E-Resources Units in their libraries. The study outcome also showed the presence of digital institutional repositories in almost all the university libraries studied. Concerning the available EIRs, it was observed that the prevalent ones are: access to free internet resources, electronic journals, online databases, and online public access catalogue. This result validates Mukhtar and Maidabino (2021) findings which revealed that the available EIRs in the university libraries they studied are electronic journals, electronic books, online databases, and CD-

ROM databases except in the area of CD-ROM databases which this study rejects its availability. The possible reason for the non-availability of CD-ROM databases could be attributed to the current technological evolutions which have brought about new and more advanced technologies that could be utilized in storing data and information.

Uses of digital libraries and EIRs in Universities in Nigeria

The findings in the area of the use of digital libraries and the EIRs showed that the majority of the users utilize them in finding relevant needed information, research activities, and completing assignments. This finding agrees with the outcome of studies carried out by Quadri, Adetimirin and Idowu (2014), Osinulu (2020), and Nwalo and Babarinde (2022) which discovered that research activities and completion of assignments were the major purposes for the respondents' use of these resources. This current study also established that the respondents use these resources because it gives them access to a wide range of information, current and up-to-date information, and also makes access to information very easy for them. This also substantiates Owolabi et.al (2016) findings that the benefits derived by undergraduate students from the use of EIRs are; access to current and up-to-date information, faster access to information, access to a wider range of information, and easier access to information.

Strategies for Sustaining Digital Libraries and EIRs in Universities in Nigeria

Strategies for sustaining digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria as established in this study include allocation of adequate funding to the libraries, development of digital repositories, lecturers subjecting students to the use of e-resources for coursework, ensuring that there is adequate subscription to needed online resources, provision of adequate internet facilities, improving ICT skills of users, conducting information literacy skills training for the user, and marketing and promotion of digital libraries and EIRs. This finding is in tandem with Urhiewhu (2015), Ogbuiyi et al (2015), and Isaac (2017) whose studies indicated the need for adequate allocation of resources, subscription of needed resources, an increase of internet bandwidth, training and retraining of users, provision of steady power supply and marketing and promotion of digital information services and resources as key factors for efficiency and effectiveness of digital libraries.

Factors that pose as threats to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria

The factors identified in this study as threats to the sustainability of digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria based on a hierarchical order are epileptic power supply, frequent breakdown of digital facilities, lack of skills to access digital information resources and databases, inadequate number of computers to access digital information resources, and inadequate bandwidth for internet access. The research outcome here corroborates with those of Urhiewhu (2015), Edem and Egbe (2016), Ankrah & Atuase (2018), and Ternenge and Kashimana (2019) whose studies revealed that epileptic power supply,

poor internet connection, limited skills, lack of formal training on internet resources' use, and insufficient subscribed titles are the factors that affect the use of these resources. While, the question if libraries can support themselves in terms of funding depends on what the libraries and library management decide to do (Irenea, Bribena & Eru, 2019), a myriad of factors above and emerging challenges will require answers from both the library and institutional managements. The implication of this is that factors that negatively affect the use of digital libraries and EIRs use will definitely affect their relevance and sustainability.

Conclusion

The establishment of digital libraries and the acquisition of EIRs without consideration of strategies for sustaining them could truncate the achievement of the goals for their existence. This investigation has revealed that there is the availability of functioning digital libraries and EIRs in universities in Nigeria. It has also identified the various types of EIRs available in these libraries as well as the purposes and benefits derived from their use by the users. The strategies identified for sustaining the digital libraries and use of the EIRs in universities are the allocation of adequate funding to the libraries, development of digital repositories, lecturers subjecting students to the use of e-resources for coursework, ensuring that there is an adequate subscription to needed online resources, provision of adequate internet facilities, training of users, and marketing and promotion of digital libraries and EIRs. The study equally revealed that factors that pose as threat to the sustainability of these resources include epileptic power supply, inadequate number of computers, inadequate bandwidth, and lack of skills among others. The implication of the outcome of this study is that librarians as professionals should be more pragmatic and put in more effort in their service delivery for the sustainability of these vital resources.

Recommendation

Based on the outcome of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The management of universities in Nigeria should budget adequate funds for the library for the purpose of equipping the digital libraries and paying for the subscription of EIRs and databases.
2. Librarians should make the training and retraining of their users in the areas of information literacy skills including online searching skills a routine so as to enable them to acquire the basic skills that will enable them to exploit the digital libraries and EIRs.
3. The Management of the universities should provide a dedicated alternate power supply for the libraries.
4. The Internet bandwidth for the libraries should also be increased for the prevention of slow internet connections.

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